

Study of Thyroid Dysfunction in Metabolic Syndrome Patients in Tertiary Care Hospital

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Abstract:

Background and Objectives: Both metabolic syndrome and thyroid dysfunction are associated with increased risk of atherosclerotic heart disease. The present study was conducted to study the Association of thyroid dysfunction and metabolic syndrome and to find out the type of thyroid dysfunction in metabolic syndrome patients.

Methods: Sixty cases were defined as metabolic syndrome according to the IDF Criteria. Detailed history and necessary investigations like fasting blood sample was analyzed for total triiodothyronine (T3), total thyroxine (T4), thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH), lipid profile, and blood glucose were undertaken.

Results: In our study population of metabolic syndrome cases, The Thyroid dysfunction is present in 16.7% patients. Among the thyroid dysfunction, sub clinical hypothyroidism is highly prevalent – 11.7%, the hypothyroidism is 3.3% prevalent in metabolic syndrome patients (one patient had TSH levels of more than 150 mU/L) and sub clinical hyperthyroidism is 1.7% prevalent. There were no overt hyperthyroidism patients in our study.

Conclusion: This study clearly shows that, one sixth of metabolic syndrome patients or every sixth metabolic syndrome had hypothyroidism either overt or subclinical. This finding indicates a need for investigating the presence of Thyroid dysfunction during managing metabolic syndrome patients.

Keywords: Metabolic syndrome; Thyroid dysfunction.

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Introduction

"deadly quartet" -- also known as "metabolic syndrome" and "syndrome X" -- is the cluster of metabolic abnormalities where in people are obese, and have hypertension, high triglyceride levels, low high density lipoproteins and abnormal fasting glucose levels. People with metabolic syndrome are at high risk for developing cardiovascular disease and are twice likely to die from and three times as likely to have myocardial infarction, stroke compared with people without this syndrome.

Insulin resistance is supposed to be the central pathophysiological phenomenon underlying the clustering. Thyroid disease is associated with atherosclerotic cardiovascular disease. This association may be in part be explained by thyroid hormones regulation of lipid metabolism and its effects on blood pressure. This hormone appears to serve as a general pacemaker accelerating metabolic process and may be associated with metabolic syndrome. Both metabolic syndrome and thyroid dysfunction are associated with increased risk of atherosclerotic heart disease. Little is known

about the relationship between metabolic syndrome and thyroid dysfunction. Only a few small studies have been performed. In a cross sectional study in 220 metabolic syndrome patients, it was found that subclinical hypothyroidism was prevalent in 16.4 % of metabolic syndrome patients. In a study from Nepal, Chandra L et al found that metabolic syndrome was prevalent in 21.1% of thyroid dysfunction patients.

The study done by Lin St et al found that lower free thyroxin level are associated with metabolic syndrome in Chinese population. There is no information available in literature regarding this association in this part of country. Therefore, the association of thyroid dysfunction with metabolic syndrome was evaluated in this study.

Aims and Objectives

1. To find out the association of thyroid dysfunction and metabolic syndrome.
2. To find out the type of thyroid dysfunction in metabolic syndrome.

Materials and Methods

Source Of Data: Patients who were diagnosed as metabolic syndrome and fulfill inclusion and exclusion criteria, getting admitted to Medical wards in GMERS Medical College, Civil Hospital Gandhinagar during the period of July 2023 to October 2024.

Sampling Method: Simple random sampling.

Study Design

- Single Center
- Nonrandomized cross sectional study

Sample Size: In the study period of 16 months among the patients attending the Dept of General Medicine after applying inclusion and exclusion criteria 60 patients were included in this study.

Selection of Study Subjects: The patients who fulfilled the criteria for metabolic syndrome by IDF who gave informed consent were taken in to the study.

For a person to be defined as having the metabolic syndrome they must have Central obesity - defined as waist circumference with ethnicity specific values (for south Asians : ≥ 90 cm for Men and ≥ 80 cm for women were used). AND any two of the following:

1. Raised triglycerides: > 150 mg/dL (1.7 mmol/L), or specific treatment for this lipid abnormality.
2. Reduced HDL cholesterol: < 40 mg/dL in males, < 50 mg/dl in females, or specific treatment for this lipid abnormality.
3. Raised blood pressure: systolic BP > 130 or diastolic BP > 85 mm Hg, or treatment of previously diagnosed hypertension.
4. Raised fasting plasma glucose :(FPG) > 100 mg/dl, or previously diagnosed type 2 diabetes mellitus.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Patients of Age more than 18 years, who fulfilled the criteria for metabolic syndrome by

International diabetic foundation [IDF] were taken into study.

2. Patients with metabolic syndrome not on any medications – newly detected metabolic syndrome patients.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Known hypothyroid or sub-clinical hypothyroid or hyperthyroidism patients.
2. Patients taking medications for diabetes mellitus, hypertension, thyroid disorders, dyslipidemia, taking steroids.
3. Individual less than 18 year's age.

Methodology

Detailed history of medication, and anthropometric measurements like height, weight, waist circumference were noted in a semi-structured proforma. Blood pressure was recorded in right upper limb in sitting posture. After eight hours of fasting, blood drawn for fasting blood sugar, lipid profile and thyroid assay in a single sitting.

Definitions: Euthyroidism is defined as TSH – 0.4 mU/L to 4.5mU/L, T4 – 5.4 microg/dl to 11.7 microg/dl. Sub clinical hypothyroidism TSH – 4.51 mU/L to 10.0 mU/L .T4 – 5.4 microg/dl to 11.7microg/dl. Hypothyroidism TSH – > 10.0 mU/L, T4 – < 5.70 ng/dl. Sub clinical Hyperthyroidism TSH – 0.1 mU/L to 0.4 mU/L, T4 – 5.4 microg/dl to 11.7 microg/dl. Hyperthyroidism TSH – < 0.1 mU/L, T4 – > 11.7 microg/dl

Results and Observations

Population Characteristics: Among the 60 patients included in our study 27 patients were men accounting for 45% of the total cases. The remaining 33 patients were (55%) women. According to the age, patients' between 30 and 39 years of age were 15 in number (25%). Majority of the patients were in the age group between 40 and 49 years - 28 patients (47% of study population) were in this group. 11 patients (18%) were between the age of 50 and 59 years. 6 patients (10%) were above the age of 60. Population characteristics are shown in table 1.

Table 1: Population Characteristics

Age	Total No	Percentage	Male	Female
30-39	15	25%	6	9
40-49	28	47%	14	14
50-59	11	18%	1	10
60-69	6	10%	6	0

According to the metabolic syndrome parameters, 60 members included in the study, 19 fulfilled three among five metabolic syndrome parameters criteria. Another 19 members fulfilled four metabolic syndrome parameters criteria and the rest of 22 members fulfilled all the metabolic syndrome criteria.

Table 2: Thyroid Dysfunction

Group	No	%	Male	Female
Euthyroid	50	83.33 %	26	24
Hypothyroid	2	3.33 %	1	1
Subclinical Hypothyroidism	7	11.67%	0	7
Subclinical Hyperthyroidism	1	1.67%	0	1
Hyperthyroidism	0	0	0	0

The thyroid dysfunction is 16.7% prevalent in metabolic syndrome patients.

Among the thyroid dysfunction, sub clinical hypothyroidism is highly prevalent – 11.7%. The hypothyroidism is 3.3% prevalent in metabolic syn-

drome patients (one patient had TSH levels of more than 150mU/L) and sub clinical hyperthyroidism is 1.7% prevalent.

There were no overt hyperthyroidism patients in our study.

Table 3: Age Wise Thyroid Dysfunction

Age	Total No	Euthyroid	Hypo Thyroid	Subclinical Hypothyroid	Subclinical Hyperthyroid
30-39	15	13	1	1	0
40-49	28	23	0	4	1
50-59	11	8	1	2	0
60-69	6	6	0	0	0

Based on the metabolic syndrome criteria, of those patients who fulfilled three of the five risk factors three had thyroid dysfunction; of the patients who had four risk factors two had thyroid dysfunction; of the patients who had all five risk factors five had thyroid dysfunction.

Table 4: Metabolic Syndrome Parameters Wise Thyroid Dysfunction

Ms Criteria Fulfilled	Total No	Euthyroid	Hypo Thyroid	Subclinical Hypothyroid	Subclinical Hyperthyroid
3	19	16	1	2	0
4	19	17	0	1	1
5	22	17	1	4	0

Table 5: Distribution of Thyroid Dysfunction

MS Parameters	Euthyroid		Sub Clinical Hypothyroidism		P Value
	MEAN	SD	MEAN	SD	
WC	97.16	6.98	98.57	8.32	0.626
SBP	139.88	14.14	140.29	14.40	0.944
DBP	89.52	7.28	88.29	9.20	0.689
FBS	158.28	51.04	141.43	37.82	0.405
HDL	43.46	6.25	43.43	4.58	0.990
TGL	234.20	170.18	185.57	93.75	0.434

(P value > 0.05 not significant at 5% level) As there were small no of patients with very high variants, statistically significant results were not found.

Table 6: Correlation between T4, TSH and Metabolic Syndrome Parameters in Euthyroid Patients

Ms Parameter	T 4	P Value	Tsh	P Value
WC	0.243	0.08	-0.029	0.839
SBP	0.078	0.59	0.076	0.60
DBP	0.125	0.38	-0.416	0.77
FBS	0.175	0.22	-0.095	0.59
HDL	0.067	0.64	-0.108	0.45
TGL	0.056	0.69	-0.066	0.30

(P value > 0.05 not significant at 5% level)

Table 7: Correlation between T4, TSH and Metabolic Syndrome Parameters in Subclinical Hypothyroid Patients

Ms Parameter	T4	P Value	Tsh	P Value
WC	6.5	0.11	-0.577	0.17
SBP	5.14	0.23	-0.511	0.24
DBP	-4.9	0.91	0.060	0.89
FBS	7.41	0.05	-0.576	0.17
HDL	4.6	0.29	-0.249	0.58
TGL	-4.04	0.82	-0.134	0.77

(P value > 0.05 not significant at 5% level)

Correlation coefficient values between T4, TSH and metabolic parameters are not significant in our study, because of limited number of study subjects and variants are high.

Discussion

The metabolic syndrome is a cluster of metabolic abnormalities wherein people are obese and have hypertension, high triglyceride level, low high density lipoprotein cholesterol and abnormal fasting glucose levels. 4 People with metabolic syndrome are at high risk for developing cardiovascular disease and type 2 diabetes.

Hypothyroidism is associated with lipid abnormalities like high triglycerides and low high density lipoproteins, weight gain, glucose intolerance and hypertension. [37] Thus hypothyroidism mimics the parameters of metabolic syndrome.

This study was conducted in 60 cases of metabolic syndrome, who had been admitted to GMERS Medical College, Gandhinagar during the period from July 2023 to October 2024. All cases met inclusion and exclusion criteria. The observations made in this study are discussed here.

Table 8. Comparison of Association of Thyroid Dysfunction in Metabolic Syndrome with Other Studies

Studies	Percentage of thyroid Dysfunction
Uzunula et al [7]	16.4 %
Chandra L et al [8]	21.1 %
P Gyawali [6]	31.25 %
Present study	16.7 %

In this study, thyroid dysfunction is 16.7% among metabolic syndrome patients. Hypothyroidism is 15% prevalent in metabolic syndrome patients (Overt Hypothyroidism 3.3% and sub clinical hypothyroidism 11.7%). The Association of thyroid dysfunction and hypothyroidism in metabolic syndrome patients are higher than in the normal popu-

lation, which is 5.9% for thyroid dysfunction and 4.6% for hypothyroidism (0.3% overt and 4.3% sub clinical hypothyroidism).

This study is consistent with study done by Uzunula et al, as 16.4% of metabolic syndrome patients had hypothyroidism in japan.

Table 9: Comparison of Age and Sex Distribution with Other Studies

Studies	Age (years)	Males	Females
Ghanshyam PS Shantha et al [6]	51± 9.4	42.9 %	57.1 %
Present study	45± 8.4	45 %	55 %

In the present study, the age incidence was more between the age group 40- 49 years and females predominated males which is comparable to the Ghanshyam study.

Table 10: Comparison of Type of Thyroid Dysfunction with Other Studies

Studies	Euthyroid	Subclinical Hypo-thyroid	Hypothyroid	Subclinical hyperthy-roid
Ghanshyam PS Shantha et al [6]	70 %	21.9 %	7.4 %	0 %
P Gyawali [6]	68.75 %	28.9 %	1.55 %	0.8 %
Present study	83.33 %	11.67 %	3.33 %	1.7 %

In this study one sixth of metabolic syndrome patients or every sixth patient with metabolic syndrome has hypothyroidism.

It is well known and proven that, by treating with

levothyroxine replacement in all overt or clinical hypothyroid patients, we can reduce all the metabolic parameters and cardiovascular risk. There is some controversy in treating sub clinical hypothyroidism patients.

Managements of patients sub clinical hypothyroidism remain controversial because the body of scientific evidence available to guide clinical decision is limited. The risk of progression from subclinical hypothyroidism to overt hypothyroid is 2-5% per year. A meta-analysis report shows that levothyroxine therapy in individuals with sub clinical hypothyroidism lowers mean serum total and low-density cholesterol concentration significantly and the reduction in serum cholesterol may be larger in individuals with higher pretreatment cholesterol levels.

Limitations of the Study

- Small number of study subjects.
- FT4 levels, could not be assessed due to financial constraints.
- We have not taken control group for the present study.

Summary and Conclusion

1. Thyroid dysfunction is common in metabolic syndrome patients and it occurred in 16.7% of metabolic syndrome patients in our study.
2. Sub clinical hypothyroidism is present in 11.7% and over hypothyroidism is 3.3% in metabolic syndrome patients in our study.
3. One sixth of metabolic syndrome patients or every sixth metabolic syndrome had hypothyroidism either overt or subclinical.
4. It is better to exclude the presence of Thyroid dysfunction while managing metabolic syndrome patients, for better outcome.

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